

THE COURSE OF CYCLISATION OF α -BENZYLHOMOPHTHALIC ACIDS.
PART I. A NEW ROUTE TO 2:3-6:7-DIBENZOTROPONES

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It is shown that cyclisation of α -benzylhomophthalic acids leads either to a seven-membered ketone (source of 2:3-6:7-dibenzotropones) or to an indeno-(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarin or to a mixture of both. Structures of both the classes of compounds have been established. An alternative route to dibenzotropones from α -benzylhomophthalic acids has been indicated.

The synthesis of 2:3-6:7-dibenzotropone and its derivatives was reported by Treibs and Klinkhammer (*Chem. Ber.*, 1951, **84**, 671; 1950, **83**, 367) and also independently by Cope and Fenton (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1673) by essentially the same route. Since then several syntheses have appeared (Bergmann and Ginsburg, *Bull. Res. Council, Israel*, 1951, **1**, No. 3, 120; Bergmann *et al.*, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1951, **18**, 684; Sorrie and Thomson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2244; Battersby and Binks, *ibid.*, 1955, 2896; Rigaudy and Nedelec, *Compt. rend.*, 1953, **236**, 1287; Leonard *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 5078; Colonge and Sibeud, *Compt. rend.*, 1952, **234**, 530) and an alicyclic approach to 2:3-6:7-dibenzotropone itself has been reported by Amiel and Ginsburg (*Tetrahedron*, 1957, **1**, 19). It appears that an alternative direct synthesis of dibenzotropones may be effected by cyclisation of α -benzylhomophthalic acids which are readily obtained by the reduction of benzylidenehomophthalic acids. The latter are easily prepared

- (II): R=OMe; R'=H; R''=COOH.
 (III): R=OEt; R'=H; R''=COOH.
 (IV): R=H; R'=Me; R''=COOH.
 (V): R=H; R'=OMe; R''=COOH.
 (VI): R=R'=R''=H.
 (VII): R=R''=H; R'=Me.

- (VIII): R=OMe; R'=H; R''=COOH.
 (IX): R=OMe; R'=R''=H.
 (X): R=OEt; R'=H; R''=COOH.
 (XI): R=OEt; R'=R''=H.
 (XII): R=R''=H; R'=Me.

(XIII)

by either Perkin's reaction or by the Stobbe condensation of aromatic aldehydes with homophthalic esters (Pinder and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2612). Thus, veratrylidenehomophthalic acid (I) (Buu Hoi, *Compt. rend.*, 1946, 211, 643) on reduction with sodium amalgam furnished 3:4-dimethoxybenzylhomophthalic acid (II). This on treatment with polyphosphoric acid at 100° afforded 2':3'-dimethoxy-2:3-6:7-dibenzo-1-suberone-5-carboxylic acid (VIII), the structure of which was followed by comparison of UV spectra (Fig. 1) with the related suberone (IX)

FIG. 1

which was synthesised independently as given below. Decarboxylation of (VIII) with the aid of copper bronze also afforded (IX) which on dehydrogenation with *N*-bromosuccinimide yielded the dimethoxydibenzotropone (XIII). The ketone (IX) was secured by using the method of Treibs and Klinkhammer (*loc. cit.*). Thus veratrylidenephthalide (Kodama, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1943, 63, 54) on catalytic reduction or by reduction with zinc dust and potassium hydroxide gave the dihydro derivative (XIV). This on treatment with potassium hydroxide at 200° under carefully controlled conditions furnished the stilbene carboxylic acid (XV) which on catalytic hydrogenation, followed by cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid, readily afforded the ketone (IX).

- (XVI): $R=OEt$; $R'=H$.
 (XVII): $R=R'=H$.
 (XVIII): $R=H$; $R'=Me$.
 (XIX): $R=H$; $R'=OMe$.

When 3:4-diethoxybenzylhomophthalic acid (III) was treated with polyphosphoric acid, a mixture of the acid (X) and an alkali-insoluble compound, $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$, was isolated; no crystalline product could be obtained from 3:4-methylenedioxybenzylhomophthalic acid (Buu Hoi, *Compt. rend.*, 1944, **218**, 942). *A priori*, the structure of the alkali-insoluble compound may be the diketone (XX: $R=OEt$) or 5':6'-diethoxyindeno-(3':2'-3:4) isocoumarin (XVI). The formation of diketones by acylation, *meta* to the carbonyl group, is well known in literature (cf. v. Braun and Wissbach, *Ber.*, 1931, **64**, 1785; Manske, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 1104). In order to investigate the formation of "diketone" in the simplest case, the cyclisation of benzylhomophthalic acid itself was studied. This compound formed only the anhydride at 100° , but at 150° a single compound, $C_{16}H_{10}O_2$, corresponding to either (XVII: $R=H$) or (XX: $R=H$) was readily isolated. The compound dissolved in sulphuric acid producing a brilliant green fluorescent solution and it also reacted with hydroxylamine to give rise to a product, $C_{16}H_{11}NO_2$, corresponding to a mono-oxime. The compound, however, showed a sharp lactone carbonyl absorption at 5.78μ (KBr pellet) supporting the structure (XVII: $R=H$). This was further confirmed on the following grounds:

(i). 2:5-Dimethylbenzylhomophthalic acid (IV) and 2:5-dimethoxybenzylhomophthalic acid (V) also underwent double cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid to yield respectively (XVIII) and (XIX), indicating thereby that *one nuclear cyclisation had taken place* and thus excluding the diketone structure.

(ii). The compound $C_{16}H_{10}O_2$ derived from benzylhomophthalic acid was lactonic in nature and was hydrolysed to the ketone (XXI) (2-*o*-carboxyphenylindan-1-one) having a similar UV spectrum as 2-phenylindan-1-one (Fig. 2).

FIG. 2

(iii). The compound, on treatment with alcoholic ammonia at 200° furnished the hydroxyisoquinoline (XXII) which was successively converted into the chloro derivative (XXIII) (by phosphorus oxychloride) and then catalytically reduced to 1:2-benzo-4-azafluorene (XXIV).

From the above result it appears that the reaction between (XVII) and hydroxylamine resulted in the formation of the *N*-oxide of (XXII). On reduction with zinc dust in acetic acid the compound indeed affords the hydroxyisoquinoline (XXII).

The brilliant green fluorescence of the compound (XXVII) in sulphuric acid is due to the formation of 1-hydroxyisobenzopyrylium salt (XXV).

It may be noted that the decarboxylation of α -benzylhomophthalic acid with potassium hydroxide at 300° yields dibenzyl-2-carboxylic acid (in poor yield) (cf. Baker *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1448). The latter has already been cyclised to dibenzosuberone by Treibs and Klinckhammer. This alternative approach has been used in the synthesis of the suberone (XII), the authentic specimen of which was secured from 2:5-dimethylbenzylidenephthalide, following Cope and Fenton (*loc. cit.*). The latter was prepared from 2:5-dimethylphenylacetic acid and phthalic anhydride in the usual manner. 2:5-Dimethylphenylacetic acid itself was synthesised from 2:5-dimethylbenzaldehyde by way of the related azlactone.

2':3'-Dimethoxy-2:3-6:7-dibenzo-1-suberone (IX) proved similar to 2:3-6:7-dibenzo-1-suberone in chemical properties. Thus, on treatment with methylmagnesium iodide, the compound readily afforded the methylene derivative (XXVI) (absorbing at 11.20μ in the infrared) and on oxidation with chromic acid gave 2:3-dimethoxyanthraquinone (XXXIV), identical with an authentic specimen (*vide Experimental*). On the Clemmensen reduction, it afforded (XXVI) along with a small quantity of the *bis*-compound (XXVIII) (having stilbene type absorption in UV) which appears to have been formed along with its geometrical isomer. The structure of the former (XXVII) was established by its independent synthesis from *o*-3:4-dimethoxybenzylbenzoic acid (XXIX) (Oliverio, *Gazzetta*, 1934, 64, 139) which was esterified and reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to the corresponding alcohol (XXX), which was next converted into

the nitrile (XXXI) by way of the related chloromethyl derivative. This indirect method of homologation of (XXIX) had to be resorted to because attempts to prepare the acid chloride of (XXIX) by the action of thionyl chloride in the projected Arndt-Eistert procedure led to the formation of 2:3-dimethoxyanthraquinone (XXXIV), evidently formed by a process of oxidation. Hydrolysis of (XXXI), followed by ring-closure, provided 2':3'-dimethoxydibenzosuberone-4-one (XXXIII). This ketone was reduced with sodium borohydride to the related carbinol which was dehydrated with the aid of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid to (XXXV) and then catalytically reduced to (XXVII).

The course of cyclisation of several other benzylhomophthalic acids is being communicated in Part II of this series.

* EXPERIMENTAL

3:4-Dimethoxybenzylhomophthalic Acid (II).—Veratrylidenehomophthalic acid (7.5 g.), dissolved in 10% aqueous NaOH solution, was reduced with sodium amalgam (450 g., 4%) and the mixture left at the room temperature with occasional stirring. The alkaline layer on acidification provided a crystalline solid mass which was crystallised from acetic acid in colorless prisms (4.7 g.), m.p. 160–61°. Buu Hoi (*Compt. rend.*, 1944, 218, 942) records m. p. 153°. (Found: C, 66.0; H, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.5%).

2:3'-Dimethoxy-2:3-6:7-dibenzo-1-suberone-5-carboxylic Acid (VIII).—The above acid (2.59 g.) was treated with polyphosphoric acid (25 g.) at 100° for 1½ hours. The viscous mass was poured into crushed ice when a solid separated on stirring. The acid crystallised from ethanol in pale yellow flakes (0.77 g.), m. p. 211° (gas evolution at higher temperature). The compound developed an instantaneous lemon-yellow colour with H_2SO_4 . (Found: C, 70.0; H, 5.2. $C_{18}H_{16}O_6$ requires C 69.2; H, 5.2%).

2:3'-Dimethoxy-2:3-6:7-dibenzo-1-suberone (IX).—The foregoing acid (0.7 g.) was heated in a metal bath at 240–50° for ½ hour under reduced pressure (100 mm) till the evolution of gas had stopped. The product was cooled, extracted with ether and washed with alkali and water. After drying the ethereal solution ($MgSO_4$), the solvent was removed and the residue was crystallised from ethanol in colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 135°. The ketone showed a lemon-yellow colour with sulphuric acid; yield quantitative. (Found: C, 76.4; H, 6.3. $C_{17}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 76.1; H, 6.0%).

2:3'-Dimethoxydibenzotropone (XIII).—The above ketone (0.5 g.) was dissolved in CCl_4 (10 c.c.) and treated with *N*-bromosuccinimide (0.4 g.) and benzoyl peroxide (0.02 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 75 minutes and filtered hot. The filtrate was refluxed with triethylamine (1 c.c.) for 1½ hours. The solution was cooled, treated with water and the tropone was crystallised from ethanol in yellow plates, m.p. 131–32°, depressed on admixture with the suberone (IX). The compound dissolved in sulphuric acid exhibiting a lemon-yellow colour. λ_{max}^{alc} 283 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.59) (Fig. 3). (Found: C, 76.3; H, 4.9. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 76.7; H, 5.3 %).

3:4-Dimethoxybenzylphthalide (XIV).—(a). Zinc dust (7.5 g.) was added in small quantities at a time to a boiling mixture of veratrylidenephthalide (5 g.), water (25 c.c.) and KOH (12.5 g.). The boiling was continued till the solution became colorless (40–50 minutes). Water was added to dissolve the potassium salt and the resulting solution filtered and acidified. The phthalide

* All m.p.s are uncorrected. UV absorption spectrum was measured in a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer (DU model).

crystallised from methanol in colorless plates (4.1 g.), m.p. 88-90°. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 5.8. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.7%).

FIG. 3

(b). The veratrylidene phthalide (1.0 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (50 c.c.) and shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen in presence of palladised charcoal (0.2 g., 5%). The hydrogenation was complete in $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours and on working up, the above dihydrophthalide, m.p. and mixed m.p. 89-91°, was obtained.

4':5'-Dimethoxystilbene-2-carboxylic Acid (XV).—The above reduced phthalide (1 g.) was treated with a solution of KOH (0.5 g.) in water (1 c.c.) and the mixture heated under reduced pressure at 200° (oil-bath) for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The product was dissolved in water and acidified. The acid (0.5 g.) separated from 90% acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 186°. (Found: C, 72.1; H, 5.7. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.7%).

4':5'-Dimethoxydibenzyl-2-carboxylic Acid.—The foregoing acid (XV, 4.51 g.) was reduced catalytically in presence of palladised charcoal (0.5 g., 15%) in acetic acid (15 c.c.). After the reduction was complete ($\frac{1}{2}$ hour) the mixture was worked up, yielding the acid (3.6 g.) in colorless prisms, m.p. 140-41°. (Found: C, 71.5; H, 6.5. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.3; H, 6.3%).

2':3'-Dimethoxy-2:3-6:7-dibenzo-1-suberone (IX).—The above acid (4 g.) was added to polyphosphoric acid (35 g.) and heated at 100° for 1 hour and then poured into crushed ice. The organic matter was taken up in ether, washed with alkali and water, and dried. The solid separating on removal of the solvent was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles (3.15 g.), m.p. 135-36°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained before. The compound did not furnish any oxime or 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

3:4-Diethoxybenzylhomophthalic Acid.—3:4-Diethoxybenzaldehyde (King *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 21) (6.1 g.) and dimethylhomophthalic ester (7.4 g.) were added to a solution of sodium (0.53 g.) in dry methanol (30 c.c.) and refluxed gently for 6 hours. The mixture was cooled and excess of

methanol removed by distillation. Water (36 c.c.) was added to the residue and the mixture extracted with ether to remove the unchanged material. The aqueous layer was heated with a 10% NaOH solution (100c.c.) and then acidified to afford the *homophthalic acid* as a crystalline mass which crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish plates, m.p. 178-79°, yield 6.0 g. (Found: C, 67.7; H, 5.8. $C_{20}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 67.4; H, 5.7%). On heating with acetic anhydride the acid gave the *anhydride* which crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 146-48°.

The above acid (9.7 g.) was dissolved in a 10% NaOH solution and reduced with sodium amalgam (200 g., 2%) at the room temperature for 48 hours. On working up in the usual manner, *3:4-diethoxybenzylhomophthalic acid* (III) was obtained in colorless plates (7 g.), m.p. 169-70°. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 6.2. $C_{20}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 67.0; H, 6.2%).

Cyclisation of (III).—The foregoing acid (III, 5.5 g.) was treated with polyphosphoric acid (40 g.) and heated at 100° for 2 hours. The resulting dark red solution was poured into crushed ice and vigorously stirred when a greenish solid separated. This was filtered, triturated with $NaHCO_3$ solution and filtered. The insoluble residue was dissolved in ether, washed with $NaHCO_3$ solution and water, dried and the ether removed. *5:6'-diethoxyindeno-(3':2'-3:4)isocoumarin* (0.9 g.) was obtained on removal of the ethereal solution. It was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow, woolly needles, m.p. 176-77°. The compound produced a brilliant green fluorescent solution in sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 75.0; H, 5.8. $C_{20}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 74.5; H, 5.6%).

The yellow alkaline solution (filtrate) was acidified and the solid obtained was crystallised from acetic acid. *2':3'-Diethoxy-2:3:6:7-dibenzo-1-suberone-5-carboxylic acid* (0.7 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish plates, m.p. 165° (gas evolution at higher temperature). (Found: C, 69.9; H, 5.5. $C_{20}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9%). Decarboxylation of this acid (0.45 g.) was done by heating in a metal bath at 250° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour under reduced pressure (3 mm). The product was cooled, extracted with ether, washed with sodium carbonate solution and water, dried and the solvent removed. *2':3'-Diethoxy-2:3:6:7-dibenzo-1-suberone* (XI) crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 91-92°, yield 0.12 g. (Found: C, 76.4; H, 6.9. $C_{19}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 77.0; H, 6.8%).

2:3-Diethoxydibenzotropone.—The above ketone (XI, 0.11 g.) was dehydrogenated by *N*-bromosuccinimide (0.08 g.) as before. The product after treatment with triethylamine was obtained as a semisolid mass. For purification, it was chromatographed on alumina column in benzene solution when most of the impurities were held back. The *tropone* was crystallised from ethanol in yellowish needles, m.p. 86°, depressed to 75° on admixture with the foregoing ketone (XI). (Found: C, 77.7; H, 6.3. $C_{19}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 77.5; H, 6.2%).

α -Benzylhomophthalic Anhydride.—Benzylhomophthalic acid (0.2 g.) was heated at 180° in an oil-bath. After the evolution of water vapour was complete, the mass was cooled and the anhydride crystallised from benzene in colorless prisms, m.p. 115°. (Found: C, 75.8; H, 5.0. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$: C, 76.2; H, 4.8%). The compound formed a yellow solution with NaOH (formation of enolic salt).

Cyclisation of α -Benzylhomophthalic Acid.—Benzylhomophthalic acid (1.0 g.) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (10 g.) at 150-60° for 12 hours. The resulting mass was poured into crushed ice and the solid separating was collected and crystallised from acetic acid. *Indeno-(3':2'-3:4)-isocoumarin* (XVII) was obtained in cream-coloured plates, m.p. 169-71°, showing a green fluorescence in H_2SO_4 (conc.), yield 0.6 g. λ_{max}^{alc} 224 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.24), 234 ($\log \epsilon$ 4.28), 310 ($\log \epsilon$ 4.31), 342 ($\log \epsilon$ 3.96) and 350 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.95). (Found: C, 82.1; H, 4.4. $C_{16}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 82.0; H, 4.3%). The compound did not furnish any 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone or phenylhydrazone. On treatment with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in pyridine solution for 4.5 hours on the

water-bath, the *N*-oxide of (XXII), crystallising from acetic acid in brownish needles, m.p. 260° (decomp.), was isolated. $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 238 (log ϵ 4.38), 253 (log ϵ 4.21), 262 (log ϵ 4.18), 284 (log ϵ 3.79), 288 (log ϵ 3.78) and 338 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 4.21). (Found: C, 76.4; H, 4.1; N, 5.7. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 77.1; H, 4.4; N, 5.6%). On reduction with zinc dust in acetic acid for 4 hours, the hydroxyisoquinoline (XXII) was isolated.

2:5-Dimethylbenzylhomophthalic Acid (IV).—A mixture of 2:5-dimethylbenzaldehyde (Hinkel *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2793) (3.15 g.) and diethyl homophthalate (5.8 g.) was added to methanolic sodium methoxide solution (0.5 g. of sodium in 15 c.c. of methanol) and refluxed gently for 6 hours. On working up in the usual manner, the *benzylidene derivative* (7.0 g.) was isolated, crystallising from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 213-14°. (Found: C, 72.6; H, 5.2. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 73.0; H, 5.4%). Reduction of this acid (5.0 g.) with sodium amalgam (150 g., 3%) at the room temperature for 48 hours provided the reduced acid (IV) which was crystallised from acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 177-78° (evolution of gas), yield 4.1 g. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 6.3. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.1%).

4':7'-Dimethylindeno-(3':2'-3:4)-isocoumarin (XVIII).—The foregoing acid (1.0 g.) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (25 g.) at 100° for 5 hours and then worked up in the usual manner. The *isocoumarin* crystallised from acetic acid in a yellowish crystalline mass, m.p. 188-90°. The compound is insoluble in cold alkali and showed a green fluorescence in H_2SO_4 (conc.). $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 236 (log ϵ 4.25), 313 (log ϵ 4.29), 326 (log ϵ 4.27) and 362 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 3.96). (Found: C, 82.6; H, 5.5. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 82.4; H, 5.4%).

2:5-Dimethoxybenzylhomophthalic Acid (V).—A mixture of diethyl homophthalate (2.8 g.) and 2:5-dimethoxybenzaldehyde (Tiemann and Müller, *Ber.*, 1881, 14, 1992) (2 g.) was added to a solution of sodium (0.2 g.) in dry methanol (17 c.c.), and the solution refluxed for 6 hours. Isolated as usual, the *2:5-dimethoxybenzylidenehomophthalic acid* (4.8 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in glistening yellow plates, m.p. 214-15° (gas evolution). (Found: C, 65.7; H, 5.1. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 65.9; H, 4.9%). This acid (3.75 g.) on reduction with sodium amalgam (280g., 2%) as before, gave the *benzylhomophthalic acid* (V) in quantitative yield. This crystallised from acetic acid in a colorless mass, m.p. 168-69°. (Found: C, 65.1; H, 5.7. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 65.5; H, 5.5%).

Cyclisation of (V).—The reduced acid (0.5 g.) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (20 g.) at 80° for 17 hours. The sticky mass separating on pouring into ice was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (0.05 g.). On recrystallisation, *4':7'-dimethoxyindeno-(3':2'-3:4)-isocoumarin* (XIX) was isolated, m.p. 238-39°. The compound is insoluble in cold dilute alkali. (Found: C, 73.6; H, 5.0; OMe, 22.5. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 73.5; H, 4.8; 2OMe, 21.1%).

2-o-Carboxyphenylindan-1-one.—The indenoisocoumarin (XVII) (0.5g.) was hydrolysed with EtOH-KOH on a water-bath for 1 hour and after removal of the alcohol it was carefully acidified. The *ketone* (XXI) crystallised from ethanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 160° (gas evolution). It gave the same green fluorescent solution in sulphuric acid as the indenoisocoumarin, obviously due to lactonisation. $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 244 (log ϵ 4.18) and 288 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 3.42). (Found: C, 76.3; H, 5.0. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.8%). The *oxime*, prepared in pyridine, darkens and melts at 238° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.6. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{N}$ requires N, 5.2%).

2-Phenylindan-1-one was synthesised from 1-phenylhydrocinnamic acid by cyclisation with polyphosphoric acid (cf. Miller and Rhode, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 2096). $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alc}}$ 246 (log ϵ 4.14) and 294 $m\mu$ (log ϵ 3.42). The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* was crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. 217-18°. (Found: N, 14.1. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$ requires N, 14.4%).

Indeno-(3': 2'-3: 4)-1-chloroisoquinoline (XXIII).—The *isocoumarin* (XVII) was heated with ethanolic ammonia (12 c.c., saturated at 0°) at 200° for 5 hours in a sealed tube. The cream-coloured mass of *indeno-(3': 2'-3: 4)-1-hydroxyisoquinoline* that separated was crystallised from acetic acid and obtained in drab needles, m.p. > 300°; yield quantitative. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 236 (log ϵ 4.24) and 329 m μ (log ϵ 4.14). (Found: C, 82.4; H, 4.9. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{ON}$ requires C, 82.4; H, 4.8%). This hydroxy compound (0.5 g.) was refluxed with POCl_3 (12 c.c.) for 1½ hours. The yellowish solution was poured into cracked ice, the entire mass made alkaline with ammonia and then extracted with benzene. The dried benzene solution was filtered through an alumina column, concentrated and the crystalline mass recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether. The *chloro* compound was obtained in nearly colorless prisms, m.p. 144-45°, yield 0.31 g. The compound does not give a picrate. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 258 (log ϵ 4.55), 303 (log ϵ 4.23), 317 (log ϵ 4.31), 348 (log ϵ 3.76) and 352 m μ (log ϵ 3.78). (Found: C, 76.2; H, 4.1. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{NCl}$ requires C, 76.4; H, 4.0%).

1: 2-*Benzo-4-azafluorene* (XXIV).—The above chloro derivative (0.2 g.) was reduced with palladised charcoal (0.2 g., 5%) in methanol in presence of KOH (0.1 g.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen at the room temperature. Absorption of hydrogen (18 c.c.) was complete in 15 minutes. The mixture was filtered, concentrated, cooled, and the *azafluorene* precipitated by water. The compound was crystallised from methanol in colorless prisms, m. p. 163-64°, yield quantitative. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 258 (log ϵ 4.59), 299 (log ϵ 4.25), 312 (log ϵ 4.31) and 344 m μ (log ϵ 3.72). (Found: C, 87.9; H, 5.1. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}$ requires C, 88.4; H, 5.1 %). The *picrate* crystallised from a large volume of ethanol in yellow prisms, m. p. 234-35° (decomp.). (Found: N, 9.3. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$ requires N, 9.7 %). The *picrolonate* was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow mass, m.p. 252° (decomp.).

Decarboxylation of α -Benzylhomophthalic Acid.—The acid (0.5 g.) was added to fused KOH (3.7 g.) and the temperature maintained for 5 minutes at 350° (metal bath). The mixture was cooled, dissolved in water and the alkaline solution filtered. On acidification, the filtrate gave a colorless mass of dibenzyl- α -carboxylic acid which crystallised from ethanol in colorless prisms, m. p. 127-29° (lit., m. p. 129-30°).

Similar decarboxylation of 2: 5-dimethylbenzylhomophthalic acid afforded 2': 5'-dimethyl-dibenzyl-2-carboxylic acid in rather a very poor yield, m. p. 116° (*vide infra*).

2:5-Dimethylphenylacetic Acid.—2:5-Dimethylbenzaldehyde (32 g.) was condensed with hippuric acid according to the procedure given for the synthesis of homoveratric acid ("Organic Synthesis", Coll. Vol. II, p. 333). The *azlactone* (30 g.) was crystallised from acetic acid in cream-coloured plates, m. p. 124-25°. (Found: N, 5.2. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires N, 5.1%). Hydrolysis of the *azlactone* and the oxidation of the resulting pyruvic acid gave a mixture of benzoic acid and 2: 5-dimethylphenylacetic acid which were separated by fractional distillation of the methyl esters (b. p. of the latter, 170-72°/80 mm). Hydrolysis with alkali, followed by acidification, furnished 2: 5-dimethylphenylacetic acid which crystallised from acetic acid in colorless plates, m. p. 130°. (Found: C, 73.2; H, 7.3. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 73.1; H, 7.4 %). The *anilide* of this acid crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m. p. 146. (Found: N, 6.3. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{ON}$ requires N, 5.9 %).

2: 5-Dimethylbenzylidene-phthalide.—A mixture of the above acid (1.2 g.), phthalic anhydride (1.0 g.) and fused sodium acetate (0.03 g.) was heated in a diethyleneglycol bath for 3 hours. The entire mass was poured into ethanol and the yellowish needles of the *phthalide* (0.7 g.) was crystallised from acetic acid in lemon-yellow prisms, m.p. 153-54°. (Found: C, 81.0; H, 5.7. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 81.6; H, 5.6%).

2:5-Dimethyldibenzyl-2-carboxylic Acid (VII).—A solution of the foregoing phthalide (1.0 g.) in acetic acid (5 c.c.) was refluxed with hydriodic acid (12 c.c.) and phosphorus (0.5 g.) for 6 hours. A heavy liquid separated during this period. The mixture was poured into water when a solid mass separated. This was extracted with ammonia and the ammoniacal solution on acidification furnished the acid (VII) (0.4 g.), crystallising from acetic acid in colorless prisms, m. p. 117°. (Found: C, 80.0; H, 7.3. $C_{17}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 80.3; H, 7.1%). The ammonia-insoluble residue contained the related *dihydrophthalide* which was extracted with ethanol and crystallised from ethanol in colorless glistening plates, m. p. 109-10°, yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 80.5; H, 6.3. $C_{17}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 80.9; H, 6.3 %).

1:4'-Dimethyl-2:3-6:7-dibenzo-1-suberone (XII).—Poor result was obtained when the above acid was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid. The foregoing acid (0.9 g.) was converted into the acid chloride by thionyl chloride (1 c.c.) in the usual manner. After removing thionyl chloride in vacuum, the residue was dissolved in dry carbon disulphide (10 c.c.) and treated with aluminium chloride (1.5 g.) and left at the room temperature. On working up the product after 12 hours, the *suberone* was obtained in the neutral fraction (b. p. 183°/1.5 mm) solidifying on cooling. This crystallised from ethanol in colorless prisms, m. p. 80-81°, developing a lemon-yellow coloration with sulphuric acid; yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 86.3; H, 6.9. $C_{17}H_{16}O$ requires C, 86.4; H, 6.8%).

2:3'-Dimethoxy-2:3-6:7-dibenzo-1-methylenesuberan (XXVI).—A solution of the ketone (IX, 0.1 g.) in ether (15 c.c.) was added dropwise to an excess of methylmagnesium iodide (ca. 2 moles). A yellow complex separated at once. After 15 minutes, the mixture was decomposed with H_2SO_4 (dil.) and the ethereal solution separated and dried. After removal of the ether, the residual oil was dissolved in benzene (6 c.c.), a trace of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid added and water removed from the boiling solution by distillation. The solid residue, after removal of the benzene, crystallised from methanol, yielding the *suberan* in colorless prisms, m. p. 91°. The compound did not contain any active hydrogen. (Found: C, 81.3; H, 7.2. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 81.2; H, 6.8 %).

2:3-Dimethoxyanthraquinone (XXXIV).—A solution of the suberone (IX, 0.2 g.) in purified acetic acid (5 c.c.) was treated with a solution of chromic acid (0.4 g.) in acetic acid (5 c.c.). The mixture was warmed on the water-bath for 45 minutes when evolution of gas took place. The whole mass was diluted with water and the material that separated was collected. On washing with dilute alkali, most of the acidic material was removed, leaving an orange residue which on sublimation furnished *dimethoxyanthraquinone* (0.06 g.). The quinone was crystallised from acetic acid in lemon-yellow needles, m. p. 239-40°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen as described below. (Found: C, 71.2; H, 4.7. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.6; H, 4.5%). The alkaline filtrate on acidification gave a slimy mass which had no tendency to crystallise.

To synthesise the anthraquinone, *o*-veratroylbenzoic acid (1.0 g.) was dissolved in H_2SO_4 (15 c.c.) and heated on the steam-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. On pouring into water the anthraquinone was obtained in quantitative yield, crystallising from acetic acid in yellow needles, m. p. 239-40°.

2:3-Dimethoxyanthrone was similarly prepared by the cyclisation *o*-veratroylbenzoic acid. The compound crystallised from acetic acid in light yellow needles, m. p. 130°. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 5.4. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.6; H, 5.5%).

2' : 3'-Dimethoxy-2 : 3-6 : 7-dibenzosuberan (XXVII).—A mixture of the ketone (IX, 0.5 g.), amalgamated zinc (10 g.), HCl (conc., 10 c.c.) and toluene (15 c.c.) were refluxed for 24 hours. The whole mass was diluted with water, extracted with ether and then the solvents removed under reduced pressure. The oily gummy residue was treated with dry ether (5 c.c.) when the bis-compound (XXVIII) (0.05 g.) separated. This crystallised from acetic acid in fluffy mass, m. p. 245-55° with prolonged sintering, indicating that the product was a mixture of the two possible bis-compounds. (Found: C, 80.4; H, 6.1. $C_{24}H_{32}O_4$ requires C, 80.9; H, 6.4%). $\lambda_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 288 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.2). The ethereal filtrate on evaporation gave the *suberan* as a gum which solidified (0.2 g.), crystallising from acetic acid in colorless prisms, m. p. 86-88°. (Found: C, 80.4; H, 7.1. $C_{17}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 80.3; H, 7.1%).

o-Veratrylbenzyl Alcohol (XXX).—On treating *o*-veratrylbenzoic acid with thionyl chloride, a yellow solution was first obtained which rapidly turned brown and then an orange-coloured compound separated in course of 1½ hours. The product was collected and identified as the anthraquinone (XXXIV), m. p. 239° by direct comparison.

o-Veratrylbenzoic acid (10 g.) was esterified with diazomethane. The methyl ester, which did not solidify, was directly reduced by dissolving in dry ether (50 c.c.) and adding it to a slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (3 g.) in ether (50 c.c.). In the beginning there was no appreciable reaction, but the reaction became vigorous towards the end. The mixture was left overnight and next day on working up in the usual manner, *o*-veratrylbenzyl alcohol (8.1 g.) was isolated, crystallising from benzene in prisms, m. p. 82°. (Found: C, 84.6; H, 7.2. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 74.4; H, 7.0%).

o-Veratrylbenzyl Cyanide (XXXI).—A solution of the foregoing alcohol (4.0 g.) in benzene (5 c.c.) was treated with phosphorus pentachloride (3.0 g.). A vigorous reaction took place at the ordinary temperature. After ½ hour, the mixture was decomposed with ice, extracted with ether and washed with water. After removal of the ether, the residue was treated with a solution of potassium cyanide (2.0 g.) in water (5 c.c.) and ethanol (2 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hours, and on working up in the usual manner a semisolid mass of the cyanide was obtained which was filtered, washed with cold ethanol and crystallised from methanol. The compound was obtained in hard prisms, m. p. 102-103°, yield 2.1 g. (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{17}H_{17}O_2N$ requires N, 5.2%).

2' : 3'-Dimethoxydibenzosuberan-4-one (XXXIII).—A mixture of the above cyanide (3 g.), acetic acid (5 c.c.), water (5 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) was boiled under reflux for 4 hours. The mixture was poured into water, extracted with ether and the acidic material extracted with sodium hydrogen carbonate. This carbonate solution on acidification gave the phenylacetic acid (XXXII) as a gum (2 g.) which had no tendency to crystallise. This was next heated with polyphosphoric acid (10 g.) at 110° for 1½ hours. On working up, the neutral matter solidified affording the *suberone* (XXXIII) which crystallised from methanol in colorless leaflets, m. p. 168°, yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 6.3. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 76.1; H, 6.0%). The *oxime*, prepared in pyridine, was crystallised from methanol in colorless leaflets, m. p. 190°. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 6.1. $C_{17}H_{17}O_3N$ requires C, 72.1; H, 6.1%).

2' : 3'-Dimethoxy-2 : 3-6 : 7-dibenzosuberan (XXVII).—The above ketone (0.16 g.) in methanol (5 c.c.) was treated with sodium borohydride (0.2 g.), added in small portions, and then left overnight. After removing methanol, the residue was treated with aqueous acetic acid when crystals of the *carbinol* (m. p. of the crude material, 225-26°) separated. This was collected,

dried, dissolved in toluene (6 c.c.) and boiled with the addition of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (3 mg.). Water was removed from the system by careful distillation (3 hours). On cooling, 2': 3'-*dime-thoxydibenzosuberene-4* (XXXV) separated (0.12 g.) which crystallised from acetic acid in silky needles, m. p. 251-53°. (Found: C, 81.3; H, 6.7. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 80.9; H, 6.4%).

A solution of the suberene (0.1 g.) in acetic acid (5 c.c.) was hydrogenated at the room temperature and atmospheric pressure in the presence of palladised charcoal (0.05 g., 5%). The absorption of hydrogen was rapid and complete in 2 minutes. On working up, the compound (XXVII) was obtained as colorless prisms, m. p. 91°, from acetic acid, identical with the suberan prepared previously.

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